

Inorganic Ion-exchangers as New Adsorbents in Peak Paper Chromatographic Studies of Metal Ions : Selective Determination of Nickel(II) and Cobalt(II) on Papers Impregnated with Chromium(III) and Tin(IV) Arsenosilicates

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The ion-exchange material impregnated on the cellulose paper is one of the useful techniques for the separation of metal ions¹. Peak paper chromatography based on the use of paper strips impregnated with sparingly soluble compounds, is a new approach in this direction^{2,3}. The present communication summarises the peak paper chromatographic studies on the papers impregnated with chromium(III) arsenosilicate (CAS) and tin(IV) arsenosilicate cation (SAS) exchangers-

Results and Discussion

The studies point out that well-defined peaks are obtained for some selected metal ions on papers impregnated with inorganic ion-exchangers. Out of the common metal ions like Cr^{III}, Fe^{III}, Mn^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}, Zn^{II}, Cd^{II}, Pb^{II} and Hg^{II} spotted on plain and impregnated papers only Ni^{II} and Co^{II} give the well-defined peaks on CAS and SAS papers. Further, the peak areas are found proportional to the metal ion concentration. The concentration range for the satisfactory results is 0.1 to 1.0 M. Below and above these concentrations of Ni^{II} and Co^{II}, the peaks were not clear. Although the effect of pH was not found to be significant at the low pH values (2 and 4) the peaks were rarely formed. Another interesting point regarding the formation of peak is the amount of the ion-exchange material loaded. It was observed that more than 3% of the material loaded was not effective for the formation of good peaks.

Straight lines are obtained when the peak area is plotted against the concentration of the metal ions thus predicting a proportionality relation

between the area under the peak and concentration of metal ions. The proportionality constant (*K*) was calculated by applying equation (1) (see Experimental). Nearly constant values of *K* (Tables 1 & 2) justify the validity of the results in the metal ion concentration range 0.1–1.0 M.

Thus, the study explores the possibility of using inorganic ion-exchange materials for the determination of some metal ions by applying the simple and novel peak paper chromatographic technique.

Experimental

Preparation of the impregnated papers: The Whatman No. 1 paper strips (18 × 2.5 cm) were dipped in aqueous solutions of stannic chloride (SnCl₄ · 5H₂O) or chromium nitrate Cr(NO₃)₃ · 9H₂O of different concentrations (1–3%) for 30 s. After drying for about 2 min the strips were dipped in the aqueous solutions of disodium hydrogen arsenate and then in the aqueous solutions of sodium metasilicate of similar concentrations for 30 s each before washing in water and finally drying in air. The paper strips impregnated with stannic arsenosilicate were designated as SAS while those impregnated with chromium arsenosilicate as CAS. Three sets of such papers (SAS-1, SAS-2, SAS-3, CAS-1, CAS-2, CAS-3) were prepared corresponding to the three different concentrations of the solutions. The total amount of the ion-exchange material deposited on a paper strip was determined by weighing a definite number of the impregnated and plain paper strips and dividing their difference by the number of strips. This amount for the various paper strips (in g) is given against them

TABLE 1—VALUES OF K FOR VARIOUS CONCENTRATIONS OF Ni^{II} AND Co^{II} ON CAS PAPERS AT DIFFERENT pH VALUES

Concn. of metal ion	CAS-1						CAS-2						CAS-3					
	Ni^{II}			Co^{II}			Ni^{II}			Co^{II}			Ni^{II}			Co^{II}		
	pH6	pH8	pH10															
0.1	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
0.2	2.09	2.00	1.62	2.90	2.00	2.20	1.98	2.10	2.80	2.20	2.18	2.34	2.40	2.30	2.00	2.10	2.20	2.11
0.3	2.00	2.00	2.10	2.30	2.80	2.30	1.98	1.87	2.01	2.00	2.07	2.00	1.52	2.10	1.99	2.40	2.10	2.10
0.4	2.00	2.30	1.80	1.97	2.27	2.00	1.90	1.90	2.13	2.12	1.76	2.13	2.00	2.00	2.00	1.80	2.00	2.00
0.5	1.80	2.66	2.30	2.50	2.60	2.50	2.00	1.90	2.35	2.04	2.13	2.58	2.07	1.99	2.09	1.90	2.09	2.00
0.6	1.95	2.00	2.50	2.00	2.50	2.06	2.00	1.52	2.18	1.92	2.17	1.99	2.05	2.00	2.00	2.14	2.14	2.20
0.7	1.80	1.80	2.10	2.13	2.00	1.90	2.00	1.69	2.03	2.05	2.03	2.02	2.00	2.00	2.20	2.00	2.12	2.12
0.8	2.00	2.60	2.00	1.87	1.96	1.51	1.80	1.69	2.04	1.91	2.16	1.99	2.09	2.05	1.99	1.97	2.03	2.00
0.9	1.90	2.20	1.90	2.00	2.18	1.80	1.93	1.60	2.16	1.91	1.94	1.89	2.00	1.89	2.10	1.93	1.83	1.88
1.0	1.98	2.00	2.18	2.12	2.50	1.97	2.00	1.79	1.80	1.97	2.11	1.92	2.00	2.00	2.13	1.90	2.00	1.90

TABLE 2—VALUES OF K FOR VARIOUS CONCENTRATIONS OF Ni^{II} AND Co^{II} ON SAS PAPERS AT DIFFERENT pH VALUES

Concn. of metal ion	SAS-1						SAS-2						SAS-3					
	Ni^{II}			Co^{II}			Ni^{II}			Co^{II}			Ni^{II}			Co^{II}		
	pH6	pH8	pH10															
0.1	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
0.2	2.09	1.80	2.20	1.98	2.50	2.30	1.79	2.50	2.30	2.40	2.70	2.20	2.10	2.30	1.90	2.20	1.98	2.40
0.3	2.08	1.91	1.87	2.01	2.17	1.98	2.00	2.00	1.87	2.04	2.70	1.76	2.28	2.10	2.06	2.40	2.30	2.10
0.4	2.18	1.83	2.20	2.18	2.00	1.91	2.20	2.30	2.25	2.20	2.50	2.18	2.20	2.40	2.40	2.20	1.87	1.92
0.5	2.06	1.89	1.92	1.96	1.94	1.90	1.93	2.13	2.50	1.80	2.40	2.00	2.30	2.50	1.82	2.50	2.25	1.89
0.6	1.96	1.99	1.95	2.00	1.80	1.75	1.80	2.00	2.19	1.84	2.00	2.10	1.80	2.30	1.85	2.20	1.85	1.79
0.7	1.73	2.10	1.90	2.30	1.91	2.08	1.95	2.20	2.10	2.00	2.00	2.24	2.30	2.00	2.23	2.40	2.15	2.04
0.8	2.07	1.92	2.11	2.10	2.10	2.05	1.95	2.00	1.84	2.10	1.98	2.10	2.20	2.10	1.90	2.00	2.20	2.50
0.9	2.19	2.04	1.97	2.10	1.86	1.98	2.20	2.00	2.18	1.80	1.84	2.10	2.20	2.30	2.34	2.40	1.87	1.82
1.0	2.12	1.88	2.10	1.97	1.91	1.98	2.00	1.93	2.20	1.85	1.97	1.94	1.82	1.98	2.13	2.04	2.20	1.98

in parentheses: SAS-1 (0.0181), SAS-2 (0.0498), SAS-3 (0.0546), CAS-1 (0.0181), CAS-2 (0.0341), CAS-3 (0.0515).

Test solutions and detection reagents: Solutions of the following salts were prepared in the concentration range 0.01–1 M by dissolving them in deionised water with a little of the corresponding mineral acids to prevent hydrolysis: $Cr(NO_3)_3 \cdot 9H_2O$, $MnCl_2 \cdot 4H_2O$, $Fe_2(SO_4)_3 \cdot 5H_2O$, $Co(NO_3)_2 \cdot 6H_2O$, $Ni(NO_3)_2 \cdot 6H_2O$, $Cu(NO_3)_2 \cdot H_2O$, $Zn(NO_3)_2 \cdot 6H_2O$, $Cd(NO_3)_2 \cdot 4H_2O$, $Pb(NO_3)_2 \cdot H_2O$, $HgCl_2$.

The presence of metal ions on paper was detected by spraying the usual detecting reagents such as aluminon (Zn, Mn, Cr), dimethylglyoxime (Ni, Co), yellow ammonium sulphide (Cd, Pb, Hg) and potassium ferrocyanide (Cu, Fe).

Buffer solutions: Buffers of different pH were prepared* by mixing the varying volumes of a 0.2 N NaOH with a 100 ml mixture of 0.04 mol each of the phosphoric, acetic and boric acids.

Chromatographic procedure: One microlitre of the metal solution to be studied was applied on the plain and impregnated papers as usual and the development was made by the ascending technique keeping the total ascent at 10 cm. The spots were then detected by spraying the specific detection reagent. Good peaks were observed for Ni^{II} and Co^{II} ions on impregnated papers, the heights of which were found to be directly proportional to

the amount of the metal ions loaded (a), the amount of the ion-exchanger deposited on the paper (U) and the area of the spot formed (S),

$$h = \frac{K(a+US)}{U} \quad (1)$$

where K is the proportionality constant. The expression is identical to the one reported earlier² for the sparingly soluble substances.

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